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WASTAGE AND STAGNATION AT ELEMENTARY SCHOOL LEVEL IN UTTAR PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

Primary education provides fundamentals of all formal education. It starts at 6 years and continues upto 10-11 years of age. Primary education is a fundamental need of life and its development. Wastage and Stagnation are two great hurdles in the way of attainment of universalisation of education in the country. The aim of the study is to investigate wastage and stagnation at elementary school level in Agra and Aligarh. The sample comprises 400 students (200 boys and 200 girls) from the affiliated schools of MADHYAMIK SHIKSHA PARISHAD, UTTAR PRADESH. The data was collected using self developed School Information Schedule (SIS). The collected data was analysed with help of statistical technique like Mean, SD, "t" value. The findings show that there is significant difference in wastage and stagnation at elementary level in Agra and Aligarh among boys and girls.

Key Words : *Wastage, stagnation, Elementary Level, UEE, dropout*

INTRODUCTION

Education is derived from the Latin word 'Educatum' which means to draw out, to foster growth and develop. Education is not the communication of information by the teacher or the acquisition knowledge by the child but the total development of the personality. Education consists of all those experiences which affect the individual from birth till death. Education is the process by which an individual freely develops his self according to his nature in a free and uncontrolled environment. It is a lifelong process of growth and development. It is not confined to the limits of time, place and individual. Any person who gives the child a new experience is a teacher and any place where this giving and receiving takes place may be termed as a school. Thus is essentially a process of growth and development which goes on throughout the whole life. Rousseau developed his philosophy of naturalism keeping this wider concept of education in his view point. Education may be defined as purposive, conscious or unconscious psychological, sociological, scientific and philosophical process which bring about the development of society in such a way that both enjoy the maximum happiness and prosperity. In short, education is the development of individual according to his needs and demands of society, of which he is an integral part.

At the primary level, India has a large private school system complementing the government run schools, with 29% of students receiving private education in the 6 to 14 age group. As per the Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) 2012, 96.5% of all rural children between the ages of 6-14 were enrolled in school. This is the fourth annual survey to report enrollment above 96%. Another report from 2013 stated that there were 229 million students

enrolled in different accredited urban and rural schools of India, from Class I to XII, representing an increase of 2.3 million students over 2002 total enrollment, and a 19% increase in girl's enrollment.

While quantitatively India is inching closer to universal education, the quality of its education has been questioned particularly in its government run school system. Some of the reasons for the poor quality include absence of around 25 percent of teachers everyday. States of India have introduced tests and education assessment system to identify and improve such schools.

There have been several efforts to enhance quality made by the government. The District Education Revitalization Programme (DERP) was launched in 1994 with an aim to universalize primary education in India by reforming and vitalizing the existing primary education system. 85% of the DERP was funded by the central government and the remaining 15 percent was funded by the states. The DERP, which had opened 160000 new schools including 84000 alternative education schools delivering alternative education to approximately 3.5 million children, was also supported by UNICEF and other international programmes.

This primary education scheme has also shown a high Gross Enrollment Ratio of 93–95% for the last three years in some states. Significant improvement in staffing and enrollment of girls has also been made as a part of this scheme. The current scheme for universalization of Education for All is the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan which is one of the largest education initiatives in the world. Enrollment has been enhanced, but the levels of quality is less.

Education has been facing some special problem like wastage, stagnation and dropouts at different level. The reasons for these problems have been studied by many researchers in the past. It is worth having a glance at the studies on these problems conducted in the recent past. Of the nine studies analysed, four dealt with the problem of wastage in school education in Assam, four examined the problem of wastage at school level in Bihar, Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh, and one study attempted to trace the incidence of dropout and maladjustment among students in relation to creativity and social structure of the school.

Wastage and stagnation were higher in rural areas than in urban and suburban areas. And it was higher at primary stage than other stages. The training of teachers had no impact on reducing wastage and stagnation. The percentage was high among girls at primary stage in Rajasthan.

Gangopadhyay found that there were more dropouts among boys and more repeaters among girls. The main cause for wastage and stagnation was the dropouts and repeaters' apathy to English and a dislike for mathematics, lack of educational guidance and poor study habits. The wastage had a relation to students intelligence, socioeconomic status, parents' education and size of the family. Another crucial problem is absenteeism mainly in government schools where the percentage was higher. Absenteeism is related to poor family background and domestic life.

The studies concentrated on empirical situations rather than on the causes and factors for stagnation except Rather's study which found a positive relation between dropouts and the socioeconomic status of the child in the classroom.

Wastage at elementary level

Year	Wastage upto class I-V (%)	Wastage upto class I-VIII (%)
1960-61	64.9	78.3
1970-71	67.0	77.9
1980-81	58.7	72.7
1990-91	42.6	60.9
2000-01	40.7	53.7
2010-11	15.0	35.0
2013-14 (expected)	12.0	30.0

Source: selected educational statistics, MHRD, Govt. of India

Review of related literature

Tilak, (1995) founded in his study that in India, the dropout rate in the Elementary Education during 1990-91 was 44.3 percent, while it was 36.3 percent during 1993-94. **Sharma, R.C & Sapra, C.L., (1967)** find in their study that the incidence of wastage and stagnation is higher among girls than among boys and the total rate of wastage and stagnation is 65.20 per cent by the time children reach grade V and 78.35 per cent by the time they reach grade VIII. **Chitkara (1961)** has given the statistics of enrollment in classes I to V in India. Out of 6.90 million children who were in class - I in 1949-50, only 2.24 million children reached class V in 1953-54. This shows a wastage 67-75 percent.

Gadgil and Dandekar (1955) The studies conducted a study in Maharashtra and find that as a minimum, four years of schooling is necessary for every child to ensure the retention of effective literacy in his later life.

Need of the study

Saikia (2014) finds in his study that the wastage among the elementary school stage learners in Arunachal Pradesh is lesser than the learners of Assam in general and wastage among the male and female learners of Arunachal Pradesh is lower than the male and female learners of Assam. In According to the **NSSO (1991)**, as many as 73 million children (in the age group of 6-14) were not currently enrolled in schools. Further, child labour has been identified as one of the important factor associated with the unaccomplishment of Universal Elementary Education. On the basis of above It is realised that the wastage and stagnation and its causes in India is a big barrier in achieving hundred percent enrolment in elementary level and the rate of dropout students is differ from one state to another. Hence it is felt that there is a need to find out the causes and effect of wastage and stagnation at elementary level in Agra and Aligarh.

Statement of the problem

This study therefore sought to find out the wastage and stagnation at elementary school level in Agra and Aligarh districts of Uttar Pradesh.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to study the wastage and stagnation at elementary school level in Agra and Aligarh district.

Hypothesis

Following hypothesis were formulated to achieve the objectives:

1. There exists no significant difference in wastage and stagnation among the boys and girls at the elementary school level in Agra.
2. There exists no significant difference in wastage and stagnation among the boys and girls at the elementary school level in Aligarh.
3. There exists no significant difference of wastage and stagnation among the urban students at elementary level in Agra and Aligarh.
4. There exists no significant difference of wastage and stagnation among the rural students at elementary level in Agra and Aligarh.

Delimitations of the study

The study is delimited to –

- The study was confined to 30 elementary schools only.
- Only the students of class V-VIII selected as the sample in the study.
- Only 400 students (200 boys and 200 girls) were identified for the present investigation.
- Only two districts of Uttar Pradesh i.e. Agra and Aligarh selected for investigation.

Method

The study is descriptive in nature. The researcher has adopted survey method. The school survey is a comprehensive study of existing conditions of school and suggests improvement wherever necessary.

Population and sample

Population of the present study include all the students studying at the elementary school level in Agra and Aligarh. The sample extracted out of this population consists of a total no. Of 400 students studying in class V-VIII From 30 elementary schools of Agra and Aligarh using incidental sampling technique.

Tools used in the study

In order to meet the needs and objectives of the study the investigator developed and used the **School Information Schedule (SIS)** as a tool. The valuable suggestions of teachers, principals and experts were incorporated .

Statistical analysis

The obtained data were subjected to statistical analysis such as mean, standard deviation and t-test to test the hypothesis. The analysis is presented and discussed below :

Table 1: Mean Score of wastage and stagnation of boys and girls in Agra

GROUP	N	MEAN	SD	“t” value	Level of significance
Boys	100	21.4	5.28	0.52	Significant at 0.05 level
Girls	100	23.7	7.24		

The result in table 1 reveals the mean score of wastage and stagnation of boys and girls in Agra. The value of **t** is 0.52 which is significant at 0.05 level of confidence. The mean score of wastage and stagnation of the boys (**21.4**) in Agra is lower than the mean score of wastage and stagnation of the girls (**23.7**) (figure 1.) it can be inferred that the wastage and stagnation of girls in Agra is comparatively higher than boys. Thus the stated null hypothesis that there exists no significant difference in wastage and stagnation among the boys and girls at the elementary school level in Agra is rejected.

(figure 1.)

Table 2 : Mean Score of wastage and stagnation of boys and girls in Aligarh

GROUP	N	MEAN	SD	“t” value	Level of significance
Boys	100	22.15	4.78	7.1	Significant at 0.05 level
Girls	100	25.6	4.89		

Table 2 shows the mean score of wastage and stagnation of boys (**22.15**) and girls (**25.6**) in Aligarh. The value of **t** is 7.1 which is significant at 0.05 level of confidence. It is apparent from mean scores of wastage and stagnation of boys is lower than girls (figure 2). It can be inferred that boy’s enrolment rate and retainsion is comparatively better than girls at elementary level in Aligarh. Thus the stated null hypothesis that there exists no significant difference in wastage and stagnation among the boys and girls at the elementary school level in Aligarh is rejected.

(figure 2.)

Table 3 : Mean Score of wastage and stagnation of urban students at elementary level

GROUP	N	MEAN	SD	“t” value	Level of significance
Agra	200	18.5	4.41	6.76	Significant at 0.05 level
Aligarh	200	21.61	4.89		

Table 3 shows the mean score of wastage and stagnation of urban students at elementary level in Agra and Aligarh. The value of *t* is 6.76 which is not significant at 0.05 level of confidence (figure 3). As the mean score of wastage and stagnation of urban students of Agra (**18.5**) is lesser than the mean score of wastage and stagnation of urban students of Aligarh (**21.61**), therefore the stated null hypothesis that there exists no significant difference of wastage and stagnation among the urban students at elementary level in Agra and Aligarh is rejected.

(figure 3.)

Table 4 : Mean Score of wastage and stagnation of rural students at elementary level

GROUP	N	MEAN	SD	“t” value	Level of significance
Agra	200	18.97	7.51	5.76	Significant at 0.05 level
Aligarh	200	25.6	7.39		

Table 3 shows the mean score of wastage and stagnation of urban students at elementary level in Agra and Aligarh. The value of *t* is 5.76 which is not significant at 0.05 level of confidence (figure 4). As the mean score of wastage and stagnation of rural students of Agra (**18.97**) is lesser than the mean score of wastage and stagnation of rural students of Aligarh (**25.6**), therefore the stated null hypothesis that there exists no significant difference of wastage and stagnation among the rural students at elementary level in Agra and Aligarh is rejected.

(Figure 4.)

Major findings

The findings of the study are:

1. There exists significant difference in wastage and stagnation among the boys and girls at elementary level in Agra.
2. There exists significant difference in wastage and stagnation among the boys and girls at elementary level in Aligarh.
3. The wastage and stagnation of male learners at the elementary level in Aligarh is more as compared to the male learners of Agra.
4. The wastage and stagnation of female learners at the elementary level in Aligarh is more as compared to the female learners of Agra.
5. The wastage and stagnation of urban learners at the elementary level in the in Agra is lower than the learners of Aligarh.
6. The wastage and stagnation of rural learners at the elementary level in the in Agra is lower than the learners of Aligarh.

Conclusion and suggestions

The above findings of the study lead us to conclusion that the wastage and stagnation among the elementary school level learners in Agra is lesser than the learners of Aligarh in general. Further, sex wise comparison also shows that wastage and stagnation among the male and female learners of Agra is lower than the male and female learners of Aligarh and settlement wise also. The area wise comparison also shows that the wastage and stagnation in urban and rural areas of Agra is lesser than the wastage and stagnation in urban and rural areas of Aligarh.

On the basis of the above conclusions, suggestions are :

- The Govt. of Uttar Pradesh should increase education budget so that conditions and facilities in elementary schools increased.
- Special care should be given to physically or mentally challenged students.
- There should be punishment for people who do not doing their work in a proper manner related to elementary education.
- Curriculum should be according to child interest.
- More attention should be given to slow learners and extra teaching arrangements for them should made.
- Reformation in economic policies should made for removing poverty.
- Emphasis should be given on adult education besides primary education.

- Examination system should improved.
- Emphasis should be put on social awareness.
- The teachers of the both districts should take care of individual differences so that wastage and stagnation rate can be minimized.

Reference

- Dr. Mondal Nityagopal, Dr. Saha Birbal , Mondal Sonjoy and Saha Chiranjib (2014),” A Cognizance on The Decreasing Rate of Enrolment in Govt-Aided Primary School in West Bengal”, international journal of scientific research, vol.-3,p.64-69.
- Saikia Anjan (2014) Wastage in Elementary Education: A Comparative Study of Assam and Arunachal Pradesh, international journal of scientific research, vol.-3,p.122-124
- Sharma R.A.,Chaturvedi Shikha,Singh K.V.(2014),”curriculum instructions and evaluation”, R.lall book depot,meerut.
- Wallia J.S.(2012),”Development of educational system in India”, Ahim Paul Publishers, Punjab.
- Jain Laxmi (2008),”dropout of girl child in school”, Northern book centre,Delhi.
- Sarin and Sarin (2008), “anusandhan vidhiya” vinod pustak mandir, Agra.
- Garret, Henri E. and woodworth R.S.(2007), statistical use of statistics in education and psychology, K.G. publishers, Ludihana.
- Dhawan M.L. (2005),”Issues in Indian education”, Isha books,Delhi.
- Aggarwal, J.C (1992): Documents on Primary Education in India (1992), Selected Education Statistics, World Overview, Doaba House, Delhi.
- Aggarwal, J.C (1986): National Policy on Education and Main recommendation of National Commission for Teachers, Doaba House, Delhi.
- Sharma, R.C & Sapra, C.L., (1967): Wastage and Stagnation in Primary and Middle Schools in India, NCERT, New Delhi.
- D.R.Gadgil and V.M. Dandekar (1955) ,Report of two Investigations - Primary Education in Satara District, Gokhale Institute of Politics and Economics, Poona,. p. 67.